

Malleability in the Expand Ad-Hoc parallel file system

Dario Muñoz-Muñoz¹[0009-0009-3574-9189],
Felix Garcia-Carballeira¹[0000-0002-5067-1502],
Diego Camarmas-Alonso¹[0000-0001-7561-3619],
Alejandro Calderon-Mateos¹[0000-0001-6185-653X], and
Jesus Carretero¹[0000-0002-1413-4793]

Computer Science and Engineering Department, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid,
Av. Universidad, 30, 28911 Leganés, Madrid, Spain.

`damunozm@pa.uc3m.es`

`{fgcarbal,dcamarma,acaldero,jcarrete}@inf.uc3m.es`

Abstract. In recent years, I/O requirements have significantly increased in applications in the knowledge areas of big data and artificial intelligence. Therefore, there is a solid motivation to improve this I/O to avoid bottlenecks in data access. For this purpose, the Expand Ad-Hoc parallel file system is being designed and developed.

Since the I/O workload can change throughout the application's execution, the file system used for those applications must be malleable enough to adjust accordingly. It may need to allocate additional resources or release existing ones to accommodate the workload necessities and not waste them.

This work introduces the Expand Ad-Hoc parallel file system design to support malleability and the initial evaluation performed on the HPC4AI Laboratory supercomputer in Torino. The results show that the malleability operations scaled well when the resources allocated to the file system were modified.

Keywords: Malleability · Expand Ad-Hoc · Parallel file system · Ad-Hoc file system

1 Introduction

In the last few years, the need for applications in areas such as artificial intelligence and big data has increased. These applications require improved data I/O to avoid bottlenecks in accessing large amounts of data. An Ad-Hoc parallel and distributed file system is being developed in the ARCOS research group, which is designed for those new needs: The Expand Ad-Hoc parallel and distributed file system ²

In [5], an initial prototype and a complete evaluation of the Expand Ad-Hoc were introduced, and the system's scalability was tested. For this purpose, the

² <https://github.com/xpn-arcos/xpn>

Marenostrum IV supercomputer [3] with up to 128 compute nodes and files up to 4 TiB was used.

In our latest work, we have introduced a novel feature to the Expand Ad-Hoc parallel file system-malleability support. This feature allows the system to better adapt to the varying workload of a workflow. We then evaluated this feature on the HPC4AI Laboratory supercomputer in Torino, using up to 32 homogeneous compute nodes.

The main goal of evaluating Expand Ad-Hoc with malleability is to study the file system’s performance and scalability when expanding and shrinking the number of Expand Ad-Hoc servers. As part of our study, we employed the IOR benchmark to test the data integrity of the Expand Ad-Hoc servers. This benchmark was chosen because it accurately measures the system’s performance when the number of servers is altered.

The rest of the document is structured as follows: Section 2 shows the State of the Art; Section 3 describes the main features of Expand Ad-Hoc; Section 4 describes the malleability model designed for Expand Ad-Hoc; Section 5 presents the evaluation results of Expand Ad-Hoc with malleability on the HPC4AI *Laboratory* supercomputer in Torino. Finally, Section 6 contains the main conclusions and future works.

2 State of the Art

FLEX-MPI [8] is an extension of MPI for dynamic load balancing of SPMD (Single Program Multiple Data) applications on heterogeneous platforms under changing external loads. It monitors application performance using hardware counters and MPI’s profiling interface, with minimal overhead and code modifications. Results from the FLEX-MPI paper demonstrate a significant reduction in execution time. FLEX-MPI will be enhanced by considering other hardware events and its integration with MPI-2’s dynamic process management features to adjust processes according to application demand and performance goals.

A different approach is Pufferscale [4], a generic resizing manager for microservices based distributed storage systems, which addresses the problem of resizing a distributed storage system by considering three optimization criteria: load balancing, data balancing, and duration of the resizing operation. Since computing an exact solution to this multi-objective optimization problem takes a long time, it proposes a heuristic that finds a good approximate solution in a much shorter time, allowing users to weigh each criterion as needed. The large-scale evaluation of the proposed heuristic with Pufferscale highlights the importance of maintaining a balance in the data to systematically guarantee fast resizing when data readout generates a bottleneck, without disadvantages in other cases. The use of Pufferscale to enable storage malleability in HEPnOS [1], a real-world microservices-based storage system, is illustrated. The study of this problem under the assumption of data replication is left for future work.

HEPnOS [1] is a distributed data service for managing High Energy Physics (HEP) information more efficiently than traditional file-based approaches. HEP-

nOS decouples the constraints imposed by file-based organizations, allowing data to be accessed and processed at its natural granularity, resulting in better scalability and more efficient use of processing cores. This is possible because HEP-nOS optimizes data access by storing small objects in its metadata. The authors demonstrate this by comparing an application developed in the file-based paradigm with a version adapted to HEPnOS, showing superior scalability in the latter.

Regarding renowned file systems, in Ceph [2], rebalancing is divided into write rebalancing, which evenly distributes storage capacity among devices to avoid saturation, and read rebalancing, which ensures an even distribution of read requests to improve performance. While write rebalancing involves moving data between devices and can affect performance, read rebalancing is a lighter operation that only involves changes in the allocation of primary devices for read requests.

In the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS), the balancer [9] is crucial to ensure that data is evenly distributed among the DataNodes in a cluster. Irregular placement can occur due to several factors, such as the addition of new DataNodes or the need to comply with replication and fault tolerance policies. The balancer provides two modes of operation: as a single execution tool or as a continuous service. In tool mode, it attempts to balance the cluster as best as possible and terminates under various conditions, such as when all clusters are balanced or no blocks can be moved. In service mode, the balancer runs as a long-running daemon service, attempting to balance the cluster in each round according to the interval settings used.

3 Expand Ad-Hoc

Expand Ad-Hoc [5] is a distributed and parallel file system that operates using ad-hoc servers. This system is specifically tailored to efficiently handle data-intensive applications, making it a helpful tool for processing large volumes of data in parallel. In this section, we will briefly describe its main features.

3.1 Expand Ad-Hoc Design

The Expand Ad-Hoc design follows the client/server paradigm, as shown in Figure 1. Clients and servers communicate using MPI, making them suitable for HPC environments.

Ad-hoc servers can be deployed in the compute nodes where the application will be executed or in different nodes. If the first case is used, they can take advantage of data locality, which will be explained later in Subsection 3.4, and may lead to offering a better I/O performance.

Expand Ad-Hoc uses the compute node's local storage (HDD, SSD, shared memory, etc.) through operating system services such as the POSIX ones.

Fig. 1: Expand Ad-Hoc architecture design.

3.2 Metadata management

Expand Ad-Hoc does not use a classic metadata manager. To manage metadata, each subfile stored on the ad-hoc server has a small header reserved for that at the beginning. While all subfiles have a space allocated for storing metadata, only the master node subfile holds this metadata, as shown in Figure 2. Expand Ad-Hoc chooses the master node among those forming the partition using a hash function on the file name, which yields a unique identifier corresponding to the file's master node.

3.3 Parallel access

Expand Ad-Hoc uses an internal virtual file handler with the associated subfiles for each ad-hoc server. This approach optimizes I/O operations by dividing each operation into multiple tasks performed in parallel on the respective ad-hoc servers.

3.4 Data locality

As mentioned above, ad-hoc servers can be deployed on the same compute nodes where the application runs. This feature allows the application to take advantage of data locality when one compute node's application process uses the data stored in this same compute node. When this happens, the Expand Ad-Hoc client can detect it and directly access the data stored in this compute node, as shown in

Fig. 2: Expand Ad-Hoc storage design.

Figure 1. This optimization reduces the overhead and latency because no remote data needs to be accessed over the network.

3.5 System call interception library

The Expand Ad-Hoc system call interception library facilitates the utilization of the Expand Ad-Hoc file system without necessitating modifications to the source code of existing applications. This is achieved by interception of POSIX system calls using the LD_PRELOAD environment variable.

When a system call is intercepted, the library first checks that the file to which the call is directed is stored in Expand Ad-Hoc. If so, the corresponding Expand Ad-Hoc API function is called. Conversely, if the file is not stored in Expand Ad-Hoc, the system will execute the corresponding `libc.so` library call.

4 Expand Ad-Hoc malleability

To implement the malleability in Expand Ad-Hoc, several methods have been developed to move data between Ad-hoc servers and allow the number of servers to expand or shrink while maintaining the data. We have developed two algorithms to expand or shrink the number of servers, which will now be explained in order of lowest to highest efficiency obtained.

4.1 Rebuild partition using the backend file system

The initial algorithm consists of several steps. First, all files from Expand Ad-Hoc local storage are moved to a shared file system between compute nodes.

The next step is to stop old servers. Then, previously moved files are moved from the shared file system to Expand Ad-Hoc local storage. Finally, start all the necessary servers. A pseudo-code of this algorithm is shown in Listing 1.

Listing 1: Expand Ad-Hoc rebuild using the backend file system.

```

1 ./expand.sh flush_data
2 ./expand.sh stop_old_servers
3 ./expand.sh preload_data
4 ./expand.sh start_new_servers

```

This method (see Figure 3) relies on a shared file system between nodes to be able to dump the Expand Ad-Hoc data files and then reload them with the new server configuration. This makes the execution speed dependent on the shared file system and its use by other users in the cluster. As will be seen in the results below (see Section 5), it is the lowest performer.

Fig. 3: Expand Ad-Hoc rebuild using the backend file system. Expand (from 3 to 4 servers) and shrink (from 4 to 3 servers).

4.2 Direct rebuilding

This next method has been developed to avoid the shared file system; for this, we have developed an MPI application, which is responsible for distributing the blocks of the data files of Expand Ad-Hoc with the new configuration of servers ad-hoc between the nodes. In this case, we consider the following two sets:

$$\begin{aligned}
 OP &= \{N_1, N_2, \dots, N_k\} \\
 NP &= \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_r\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where the OP includes the servers of the old partition, and NP includes the servers of the new partition.

The MPI application is executed in the nodes of the $OP \cup NP$ set and works as follows: this application executes one process per node on the nodes of the old ad-hoc servers (OP), from now on called reader and executes another process per node on the nodes of the new ad-hoc servers (NP), from now on called writer. As can be seen in Figure 4 which shows an example of expansion with three reader processes in the old servers ($OP = \{Node_0, Node_1, Node_2\}$) and four writer processes in the new servers ($NP = \{Node_1, Node_2, Node_3, Node_4\}$), a total of seven processes will be launched. Also, in Figure 4, you can see an example of a shrink of four reader processes to three writer processes, with seven processes in total. In this case $OP = \{Node_1, Node_2, Node_3, Node_4\}$ and $NP = \{Node_0, Node_1, Node_2\}$.

Fig. 4: Expand Ad-Hoc rebuild using direct rebuilding. Expand (from 3 to 4 servers) and shrink (from 4 to 3 servers).

In this approach, each reader is responsible for calculating the subfile where each block is stored, reading that data block, and sending it to the chosen writer. The writers are simply waiting for blocks and their positions to be written. This can be seen in pseudo-code in Listing 2.

Listing 2: Expand Ad-Hoc reader and writer direct rebuild.

```

1 Reader_i(){
2   B=List of blocks of subfile i
3   for (b in B) {
4     NewServer = Compute_new_server(b);
5     NewOffset = Compute_new_offset(b);
6     DataBlock = ReadBlock(LocalSubfile, BlockSize);
7     Send(NewServer, DataBlock, NewOffset, BlockSize);
8   }
9 }
10
11 Writer_j(){
12   while(are_block_remaining()) {
13     (DataBlock, NewOffset) = Receive();
14     WriteBlock(LocalSubfile, BlockSize, NewOffset, DataBlock);
15   }
16 }

```

Other than that, it works like the other method; first, the old servers are stopped, then the block distribution is done, and finally, all the new servers are turned on. This can be seen in pseudo-code in Listing 3.

Listing 3: Expand Ad-Hoc direct rebuild.

```

1 ./expand.sh stop_old_servers
2 ./expand.sh rebuild_direct
3 ./expand.sh start_new_servers

```

5 Evaluation

This section presents the performance evaluation of Expand Ad-Hoc with scalability support when expanding or shrinking servers. For this evaluation, the IOR benchmark was used to generate the data at the beginning of the work and after the rebuild to check its integrity, thanks to an internal hash function, to ensure that it remained correct. The open source IOR³ benchmark is widely used for the evaluation of parallel and distributed file systems as it allows to simulate different I/O loads (read/write operations, shared/individual file access, etc.) and to obtain the bandwidth archived.

The evaluation has been conducted in the *HPC4AI Laboratory* cluster at Torino, described in Table 1. This cluster has a total of 2448 processors and 8.50 TiB of main memory.

Table 1: Summary of the *HPC4AI Laboratory*.

Attribute	<i>HPC4AI Laboratory</i> [7]
Number of nodes	68 nodes
Provider	Lenovo NeXtScale nx360 M5
Network	100 Gb Omni-Path
CPUs per node	2 x Intel Xeon CPU E5-2697 v4 36 processors, at 2.3 GHz
SSD per node	110 GiB
RAM per node	125 GiB
Operating System	Ubuntu 20.04.5 LTS
MPI Distribution	MPICH 4.1.1
GCC version	9.4.0
SLURM version	22.05.5

The tests have been performed as follows: first, X number of servers are turned on and through the IOR in write mode with a time signature generated data files of size 16 GiB; the time signature is so that the IOR can internally generate a hash of the files, which is then used to check the integrity of data. After this, the number of servers is changed to Y servers; this is done with the

³ <https://github.com/hpc/ior>

different versions of rebuild explained before (see Section 4), backend rebuild (*Br*), and direct rebuild (*Dr*). Then, the time calculation is done, shown in Figure 5. Finally, after making this change of servers, an IOR is executed in read mode to check the integrity of the data.

It should be noted that the shared file system used by the backend rebuild (*Br*) algorithm in the tests is the BeeGFS [6] parallel file system.

All tests used one Expand Ad-Hoc server per compute node (from 8 to 32). Each test was run as an individual job with the compute nodes in exclusivity using the SLURM (Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management) queuing system [10].

In Figure 5, are shown a column for each test performed, labeled with the algorithm used and labeled from X to Y servers. The different times it takes to distribute the data, start the servers, and stop them within the rebuild can be shown within each column.

The performance results of the different rebuild versions show the algorithm's scalability, as it reduces the execution time as the number of new servers increases. It can be shown that when an expansion from eight servers to Y servers is performed, the more servers are expanded (Y servers), the more performance improvement is obtained. When shrinking servers from 32 to Y, it can be seen that the higher the Y, the better the scalability. With these results, we can determine that our application bottleneck is the number of writer processes we have, that is, the new number of servers. This is because performance improvement is only achieved by making changes by increasing the number of new writer processes.

It is important to note that the backend rebuild algorithm gets worse results than the direct rebuild algorithm because it performs two operations: one download and one upload on the shared file system, unlike the direct rebuild version, which simply exchanges data between readers and writers without passing through any shared file system. Another noteworthy observation is the influence of block size on the performance of the backend rebuild algorithm. Particularly, in tests with a block size of 64 KiB, the backend rebuild version shows inferior performance compared to other block sizes. This can be attributed to the shared file system, BeeGFS, which appears to operate at a slower pace with smaller block sizes due to the increased number of read and write requests.

Generally, the best version of the algorithm is the direct rebuild algorithm since it directly sends the data through MPI between the servers; these do not generate other types of bottlenecks. This is demonstrated by calculating the average bandwidth of each algorithm. For the 512 KiB block size, we get a backend rebuild of 1345 MiB/sec and a direct rebuild of 2175 MiB/sec. As can be seen, the direct rebuild version is the best-performing algorithm. For the other block sizes, the order from best to worst bandwidth is also maintained.

In Figure 6, are shown a column for each test performed, labeled with the number of parallel files moving at a time and labeled from X to Y servers. Also, in the graphs below, the percentage improvement achieved by parallelizing the files can be seen.

Fig. 5: Rebuild in Expand Ad-Hoc with malleability. It shows the seconds to rebuild the data, stop the old servers, and start the new ones in Expand Ad-Hoc containing 16 GiB of data with different numbers of servers with different transfer sizes (64 KiB, 512 KiB, and 4 MiB), compute nodes (8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, and 32). Also with different versions of the *Br* (backend rebuild) and *Dr* (direct rebuild) algorithms.

It is demonstrated with these results that a considerable improvement is achieved by performing parallelism, achieving with two files in parallel an average improvement of 15%, among all the tested configurations and with four files an improvement of 25%. In order to understand why the total time of execution increases in the graphs, it is necessary to emphasize that each file is 16 GiB, and that when two files are reconfigured, they will be 32 GiB of data. Four files would be 64 GiB of data. However, this does not increase linearly, because there is an improvement, which is the commented one, obtaining up to 25% improvement in average.

Fig. 6: Rebuild in Expand Ad-Hoc with malleability in parallel. It shows the seconds to rebuild the data, stop the old servers, and start the new ones in Expand Ad-Hoc containing Z 16 GiB data files in parallel with different numbers of servers with transfer sizes of 512 KiB, compute nodes (8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, and 32). With the algorithm *Dr* (direct rebuild). The ones below show the percentage improvement over moving the same amount of data sequentially with Z files in parallel.

6 Conclusions and Future works

This work introduces the Expand Ad-Hoc parallel file system with a malleability design for HPC environments. It also introduces two approaches: one using a shared file system and the other performing data distribution using MPI. In addition, it has been evaluated at the *HPC4AI Laboratory* cluster in Turin using IOR benchmarks to test data integrity when expanding and shrinking the number of ad-hoc servers.

As seen in the evaluations presented in this work, the Expand Ad-Hoc design with malleability provides good scalability. Expanding and shrinking the servers of Expand Ad-Hoc has been shown to achieve a bandwidth of 2 GiB/sec. It takes less than 10 seconds to scale to any configuration from 8 to 32 servers for 16 GiB data. It was also found that reconfiguring the data in parallel, with four files in parallel, achieved a 25% improvement.

In future work, other algorithms to perform the data distribution will be studied. It is also proposed to implement and evaluate some designs in which the expanding or shrinking does not have to distribute the existing data to the new configuration to eliminate the distribution time.

Acknowledgments. This work has been partially funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation project “Expand: High Performance Storage System for HPC

and Big Data Environments”. Ref. TED2021-131798B-I00. And partially funded by the “Adaptive multi-tier intelligent data manager for Exascale (ADMIRE)” project of the European Union’s Horizon 2020 JTI-EuroHPC research and innovation programme. Ref. H2020-JTI-EuroHPC-2019-1, Project no. 956748. And partially supported by the EuroHPC project “Adaptive multi-tier intelligent data manager for Exascale” under grant 956748 — ADMIRE — H2020-JTI-EuroHPC-2019-1 and by the Agencia Española de Investigación under Grant PCI2021-121966.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

1. Ali, S., Calvez, S., Carns, P., Dorier, M., Ding, P., Kowalkowski, J., Latham, R., Norman, A., Paterno, M., Ross, R., Sehrish, S., Snyder, S., Soumagne, J.: Hepnos: a specialized data service for high energy physics analysis. In: 2023 IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium Workshops (IPDPSW). pp. 637–646 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPDPSW59300.2023.00108>
2. authors, C., contributors: Balancing in Ceph; Ceph Documentation — docs.ceph.com. <https://docs.ceph.com/en/latest/dev/balancer-design/> (2024), accessed May. 15, 2024. [Online]
3. BSC: MareNostrum specification (2023), <https://www.bsc.es/marenostrum/marenostrum/technical-information>, accessed March. 18, 2024. [Online]
4. Cherière, N., Dorier, M., Antoniu, G., Wild, S.M., Leyffer, S., Ross, R.: Pufferscale: Rescaling hpc data services for high energy physics applications. In: 2020 20th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Internet Computing (CCGRID). pp. 182–191 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCGrid49817.2020.00-75>
5. Garcia-Carballeira, F., Camarmas-Alonso, D., Caderon-Mateos, A., Carretero, J.: A new ad-hoc parallel file system for HPC environments based on the Expand parallel file system. In: 2023 22nd International Symposium on Parallel and Distributed Computing (ISPDC). pp. 69–76 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISPDC59212.2023.00015>
6. Herold, F., Breuner, S., Heichler, J.: An introduction to beegfs. ThinkParQ, Kaiserslautern, Germany, Tech. Rep (2014)
7. HPC4AI: HPC4AI laboratory specification (2024), <https://hpc4ai.unito.it/>, accessed March. 18, 2024. [Online]
8. Martín, G., Marinescu, M.C., Singh, D.E., Carretero, J.: Flex-mpi: An MPI extension for supporting dynamic load balancing on heterogeneous non-dedicated systems. In: Wolf, F., Mohr, B., an Mey, D. (eds.) Euro-Par 2013 Parallel Processing. pp. 138–149. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg (2013). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-40047-6_16
9. Members, A.H.P.: Apache Hadoop 3.3.6; HDFS Users Guide — hadoop.apache.org. <https://hadoop.apache.org/docs/stable/hadoop-project-dist/hadoop-hdfs/HdfsUserGuide.html#Balancer> (2024), accessed May. 15, 2024. [Online]
10. SLURM: Slurm workload manager (2023), <https://slurm.schedmd.com/documentation.html>, accessed March. 18, 2024. [Online]